
RELIGION VS SOCIETY: CASE OF WOMEN INHERITANCE IN PASHTUN TRIBES OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Society and religion are interconnected ideas that affect and impact one another differently. A person's relationship with Allah Almighty (God) or the supernatural is shaped by their religious beliefs, practices, and values. It frequently entails the worship of a deity or deities as well as the study of sacred writings and beliefs. Religion can also give people a moral compass, solace, and purpose in their daily lives. The term "society" on the other hand, describes the group of people who share a particular geographic location and who also share a shared culture, language, and set of values. In many traditional Pashtun tribes in Pakistan, inheritance is patrilineal, meaning that property is passed down from father to son. This often means that women are not entitled to inherit property. However, in some cases, a daughter may receive a portion of her father's property if there are no male heirs. In recent years, there has been a growing movement to challenge these traditional practices and promote greater gender equality in inheritance.

This has been driven by a combination of factors, including increased education and awareness, as well as changes in the broader cultural and political context. Some groups and activists are advocating for a more equitable distribution of inheritance, taking into account the needs and contributions of both men and women. It is important to note that these practices vary greatly between different Pashtun tribes, and even within the same tribe, and they are also subject to change over time. Additionally, while traditional practices may persist in rural areas, they may be less prevalent in urban areas or among more educated and progressive Pashtuns.

In general, the issue of women's inheritance in Pashtun tribes remains a complex and contentious one, and there is ongoing debate and discussion about the best ways to promote greater gender equality in this area. Islam is a religion of peace and equality, women have the right to inherit a certain portion of their father's, husband's, brother's, and son's property.

Keywords: Pakistan, Religion, Society, Islam, Women inheritance, Pashtun tribes.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7698663](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698663)